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Lord Rama as a communicator: Excerpts from Shriramcharitmanas

Mayank Bharadwaj¹, Dr Paramveer Singh²

Abstract

All know the importance of communication. For a successful life, good communication skill is essential. It gives success in job, study, maintaining relations, career etc. All like a good communicator. India has a vast population of theists who idealize lord Rama. Rama was a king, an obedient son, a loving husband and a caring brother. Apart from these, he was also a good communicator. For lord Rama's story, many books are available. In this paper, the researcher chose Shriramcharitmanas by Goswami Tulsidas to explore Lord Rama as a communicator. There are different incidents in which Rama achieved his goal only through his communication skills. In this paper, Dhanushbhang and Bharat Milan, two incidents are chosen to see the communication qualities of Lord Rama. In both of these situations, Rama excelled in communication skills. In the first incident, his conversation was with an outraged person; in the second incident, the other person was deeply sad and emotional; in both cases, Rama did very well. Some orating qualities which appeared in this study are using appropriate gestures, smiling while necessary, not using satire etc.

Keywords: *Indian Mythology, Chaupai, Prasang, Lord Rama, Shriramcharitmanas, Religious Communication*

Introduction

Communication is essential for life. Whether it is business, development or social life, communication plays an important role.

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Heads of organizations must have effective communication quality for the organisation's success. The success of any business lies in effective communication (Radovic Markovic and Salamzadeh). Communication is not only for humans; every living being communicates with each other. The success of an executive is often judged in terms of his ability to communicate. Sometimes this ability to communicate assumes more importance than the domain knowledge of the individual (T.S.). Some researches even show that plants communicate with other plants. Plants perceive their state and many aspects of their surroundings and adjust to numerous traits depending upon these conditions (Gagliano et al.).

Religion has a strong influence on how humans conduct themselves and how their behavior is modified by what their religion and its various aspects interpret to be the proper behavior (Ano and Vasconcelles). From education to family values to coping with stress, religion dictates behavior across genres. For the management of grief, religion has been positively related to incidents of death and the processing of grief in cases of the loss of a child (McIntosh et al.). Even in managing stress during a health crisis, religion has been established to play an important and positive role (AP and PA).

Communication as a specific subject of study emerged only in the 20th century. It was essentially separately studied under political sciences, sociology and psychology among others before being brought together under one umbrella dedicated to studying its various forms. Initially, it included the eternalization of religion, especially in the context of how religious leaders and the 'Gods' spoke of and communicated their messages across generations (Pooley). A stress on intrapersonal communication or communication with self to understand and delve into within with a focus on self-realization has been established as a powerful medium of communication through the academic discourse of the Vedas. It means that too successful in communicating an idea, self-realization is highly crucial and communication with the self has to be established first to communicate with others successfully (Singh).

Religious literatures have emphasized the importance of communication. *Madhumatim Vacham Vadatu Shantivam* (*Atharva*, 3.30.2) (Singhdeo Dharmendra Kumar, n.d.), which means a man

should speak what he observes through his eyes. Another verse *Sambhshanmanah priyo hai va bhavati* (Singhdeo Dharmendra Kumar) means, Well speaker is loved by all. So, everybody needs to be a good communicator. Buddhist texts also have concepts related to communication. There are three major areas related to communication that have been discussed. The samsara or wheel of life representing the wheel of life as a circular form of human communication, Yuan or the dependent originations stressing on the different elements in a communication process including the sender, receiver and channel, all having their own unique role and the concept of non-duality which opens up the possibility of changes in the communication process at the decoding and encoding level, transcending over time and space (Chuang and Chen). Sadharanikaran is a theory which came from the Indian-origin religious text 'Natyashashtra'. The Sadharanikaran theory resists on Sahridayata. Sahridayata is a concept which explains that both the communicating parties want to achieve the same state of mind which are called Sahridaya and the process is known as Sahridayata (Adhikari).

From a communication perspective, *Gita* is also studied. *Gita* is basically verbal communication whereas non-verbal communication can also be found. In this interpersonal communication, 12 appeals of influential communication like emotional appeal, rational appeal, inquisitive appeal, and devotional appeal among others (Goyal). Apart from that, many other interpersonal, intra-personal, group and mass communication references are also found in both epics (Loknath).

Two facts can be established. First, religious texts are a great source of inspiration. Secondly, religious texts are full of new information for communication scientists. Researchers have been working on different religious texts, but it is still like an ocean drop. So, in this paper, we will discuss Lord Rama's qualities as a communicator on the basis of *Shriramcharitmanas*.

Methodology

A qualitative research approach is used for this paper. The method is content analysis.

Since the *Shriramcharitmanas* is not written in English, the first

step was to translate its essence into English with an apt description of the context.

The sampling technique was purposive. Two Prasangs (events) were selected purposively from *Shriramcharitmanas*. In the second step, couplets were selected by different speakers purposively from mentioned events.

In this paper, since prior literature was absent, the coding was based on summative content analysis where the coding was done on the sentiments and themes counted and compared to establish the prowess and the features of Rama's communication approach.

Findings

Dhanushbhang

Janak, the king of Mithila, wanted to marry his daughter Sita. The king wanted to marry his girl to a man with great power. So, he organized a swayamvara and invited kings from all over the world. He put a condition in the swayamvara to pick up the bow 'Pinak', which was given to his ancestors by lord Shiva. It was tough for anyone to pick up the bow. Only a person with God's grace can pick it up. In that swayamvara, lord Rama not only picked it up but he also broke the bow. Lord Parshuram was a devotee of lord Shiva. He came very angrily to the court of king Janak. He was very angry by the damage done to the bow. He wanted to punish the person who was responsible for the act. In court, he exchanged dialogues with Rama and his younger brother Laxmana(Tulsidas).

The chaupais of this incident will be analyzed in order to find the communicative qualities of Rama.

नाथ संभुधनु भंजनिहारा । होइहि केउ एक दास तुम्हारा ॥
 आयसु काह कहिअ किन मोही । सुनि रिसाइ बोले मुनि कोही ॥
 सेवकु सो जो करै सेवकाई । अरि करनी करि करिअ लराई ॥
 सुनहु राम जेहिं सिवधनु तोरा । सहसबाहु सम सो रिपु मोरा ॥

Meaning

Lord, the person who broke lord Shiva's bow, must be your servant. Please order me, what do you want. Sage angrily said that a servant serves his master. If you are acting as an enemy, then we must fight. Rama! Listen! Whoever broke the bow of lord Shiva is an enemy like Sahastrabahu to me.

Analysis

Rama knew that Parshuram is very angry. His anger can be seen

when he compares the man who broke the bow to Sahastrabahu. As Parshuram came very angrily, Rama said very politely. He presents himself as a servant but at the same time, he is not revealing that he himself broke the bow. He knew that if he revealed himself as the man who broke bow, this would work as a fuel to fire and would surely increase the anger of Parshuram.

सुनि मुनि बचन लखन मुसुकाने । बोले परसुधरहि अपमाने ॥
 बहु धनुहीं तोरीं लरिकाई । कबहुँ न असि रिस कीन्हि गोसाईं ॥
 लखन कहा हँसि हमरें जाना । सुनहु देव सब धनुष समाना ॥
 बिहसि लखनु बोले मृदु बानी । अहो मुनीसु महा भटमानी ॥
 पुनि पुनि मोहि देखाव कुठारू । चहत उड़ावन फूँकि पहारू ॥
 कोटि कुलिस सम बचनु तुम्हारा । ब्यर्थ धरहु धनु बान कुठारा ॥

Meaning

After hearing sage, Laxmana smiled and said derogatorily, we broke many bows in childhood but you never got angry. Laxmana said laughingly, lord! All bows are equal for us. Laxmana replied smilingly; sage thinks himself an extraordinary warrior. He is flaunting his axe like he wants to blow away a mountain. Your words are like crores of thunder and you need not to hold bow and axe.

Analysis

Laxmana is smiling and satirizing Parshuram. This behaviour is making him angrier. Laxmana is trying to point out that Parshuram's only work is to express anger when any bow is damaged. Sage has a deep faith in the bow, but Laxmana compares it with any general bow. Laxmana also challenges the sage's power and capability in the second last chaupai. In the last chaupai, Laxmana is again using satire against sage in a very harsh manner. Such dialogues and ways of expression are enough to increase the anger and heat up the situation. The anger of Parshuram can be seen in his words.

रे नृप बालक काल बस बोलत तोहि न सँभार ।
 धनुही सम तिपुरारि धनु बिदित सकल संसार ॥
 बालकु बोलि बधउँ नहिं तोही । केवल मुनि जइ जानहि मोही ॥
 बाल ब्रह्मचारी अति कोही । बिस्व बिदित छत्रियकुल द्रोही ॥
 तुम्ह तौ कालु हाँक जनु लावा । बार बार मोहि लागि बोलावा ॥
 सुनत लखन के बचन कठोरा । परसु सुधारि धरेउ कर घोरा ॥
 सुनि कटु बचन कुठार सुधारा । हाय हाय सब सभा पुकारा ॥

Meaning

Prince! You are in control of death, so you are not talking sense. Is

this great bow of Shiva, known by the whole world is any other bow? I am not killing you because you are a child. You fool! Do you think that I am only a sage? I am very aggressive. The world knows well about me that I am the enemy of Kshatriyas. Laxmana said, Sage, you are summoning death again and again. After hearing Laxmana's harsh words, the sage took axe in his hands. Agitated by Laxmana's words, Parshuram picks up his axe, making the entire court gasp in horror.

Analysis

Parshuram was very angry with Laxmana as he was repeatedly using harsh and rude words filled with sarcasm. Parshuram's anger can be seen in his words when he wants to kill him but he considers Laxmana a child so he is not killing Laxmana. Parshuram's action like holding axe pointed towards Laxmana or changing the position of the axe continuously, is enough to understand his anger.

Now see the dialogues by Rama.

नाथ करहु बालक पर छोहु । सुध द्रुधमुख करिअ न कोहु ॥
 जौ पै प्रभु प्रभाउ कछु जाना । तौ कि बराबरि करत अयाना ॥
 जौ लरिका कछु अचगारि करहीं । गुर पितु मातु मोद मन भरहीं ॥
 करिअ कृपा सिंसु सेवक जानी । तुम्ह सम सील धीर मुनि ग्यानी ॥
 प्रभुहि सेवकहि समरु कस तजहु बिप्रबर रोसु । बेषु बिलोकैं कहेसि कछु बालकहू नहिं
 दोसु ॥
 देखि कुठार बान धनु धारी । भै लरिकहि रिस बीरु बिचारी ॥
 नामु जान पै तुम्हहि न चीन्हा । बंस सुभायँ उतरु तेहिं दीन्हा ॥

Meaning

Oh lord! Please be kind to your child. He is so naive; he did not know about you. If he had known you, he had not have behaved like this. If a child does freakishness, Guru and parents feel happy about it. A gentle, passionless and wise sage like you must forgive him. There is no fight between boss and servant. Leave your anger. The boy thought that you are a fighter so he said that. He saw an axe, bow and arrow with you and got angry. He had known your name but he had not seen you. So, he reacted according to our lineage.

Analysis

In the words of Rama, we can see that he regularly compares Laxmana with a child. He is asking Parshuram to forgive Laxmana and also giving a reason. Here, we can see that Rama is speaking

very clearly. He is trying to calm down Parshuram by praising him and at the same time he is reducing the importance of Laxmana and his words by comparing him to a child. Rama is trying to save Laxmana so he says that Laxmana misunderstands him as a fighter (Kshatriya). Rama justifies the Laxmana's challenge to Parshuram by explaining Parshuram as a Kshatriya.

सुनि लछिमन बिहसे बहुरि नयन तरेरे राम ।
गुर समीप गवने सकुचि परिहरि बानी बाम ॥

Meaning

Laxmana was smiling at Parshuram. Rama stared at him and Laxmana went to guru Vishwamitra and stopped speaking to Parshuram.

Analysis

Rama is not only trying to calm Parshuram but also stopping Laxmana because he is increasing the heat of the situation. Rama is trying to solve the problem but Laxmana's body language and words are not helping him. Here, his staring at Laxmana is non-verbal communication. This communication resulted in the silence of Laxmana. A good communicator must be aware of such things in any conversation.

अति बिनीत मृदु सीतल बानी । बोले रामु जोरि जुग पानी ॥
सुनहु नाथ तुम्ह सहज सुजाना । बालक बचनु करिअ नहिं काना ॥
बरै बालकु एकु सुभाऊ । इन्हहि न संत बिदूषहिं काऊ ॥
तेहिं नाहीं कछु काज बिगारा । अपराधी मैं नाथ तुम्हारा ॥

Meaning

Rama said humbly with reverence, dear lord, you know everything; you are intelligent. Please ignore this child. Children are as same as a wasp. Saint does not blame them for anything. He had done nothing wrong to you. I am the one who broke your bow. I am your culprit.

Analysis

Here, Rama is again comparing Laxmana to a child. By saying the same thing repeatedly, Rama is saying that Laxmana is a child and nothing else and it is a child's behaviour to make mischief. A wasp makes unwanted noise thus, Rama is saying that the words of Laxmana are unwanted and must be ignored. In this chaupai, firstly, he is saying to ignore Laxmana and reveal himself to divert

Parshuram's attention from Laxmana to himself. This was a great move of revealing himself at the right time. Rama realized that it would not be good for anyone if he was doing any further delay in revealing himself.

कृपा कोपु बहु बँधब गोसाईं । मो पर करिअ दास की नाई ॥
 कहिअ बेगि जेहि बिधि रिस जाई । मुनिनायक सोइ करौं उपाई ॥
 राम कहेउ रिस तजिअ मुनीसा । कर कुठारु आगें यह सीसा ॥
 जेहिं रिस जाइ करिअ सोइ स्वामी । मोहि जानिअ आपन अनुगामी ॥
 जौं तुम्ह औतेहु मुनि की नाई । पद रज सिर सिसु धरत गोसाईं ॥
 छमहु चूक अनजानत केरी । चहिअ बिप्र उर कृपा घनेरी ॥

Meaning

So lord! Rage, mercy or even if you want to kill, please do with me as I am your servant. Please take steps which will cause your anger to vanish. Rama said, my head is in front of your axe. Do whatever you like. I am your follower, so do whatever it takes to calm yourself. He must have bowed down to you if you had come as a sage. Brahman's heart is filled with mercy, so please forgive his mistake.

Analysis

Rama is showing pettiness with his words. He is declaring that he will not oppose any action of Parshuram which can calm Parshuram. He is also establishing himself as his follower, so he will not deny his order or desire. In both the chaupai, he requests Parshuram to take desirable actions to calm himself even if those actions need Rama's life. We can see how desperate Rama is to solve the situation. Here, one more thing which can be observed is the body language of Rama. He is saying with his head down or presenting his head to Parshuram to kill him.

हमहि तुम्हहि सरिबरे कसि नाथा । कहहु न कहाँ चरन कहँ माथा ॥
 राम माल लघुनाम हमारा । परसु सहित बड़ नाम तोहारा ॥
 देव एकु गुनु धनुष हमारें । नव गुन परम पुनीत तुम्हारें ॥
 सब प्रकार हम तुम्ह सन हारे । छमहु बिप्र अपराध हमारे ॥
 राम कहा मुनि कहहु बिचारी । रिस अति बड़ि लघु चूक हमारी ॥
 छुअतहिं टूट पिनाक पुराना । मैं केहि हेतु करौं अभिमाना ॥

Meaning

There is no comparison between you and me. You are like head and I am feet. My name is small, i.e., Rama and yours are bigger. I have only one quality of fighting but you have nine divine qualities.

At every level we are beneath you. Kindly forgive us. Lord! Please think before you speak. Your anger is much bigger than my mistake. The bow was ancient. I only touched it and it broke.

Analysis

In the above chaupai, it can be seen that Rama is also praising Parshuram with good words. He is explaining about Parshuram's value and his position in front of him. He is establishing the greatness of Parshuram. Sometimes it helps in calming anyone if you praise them. Rama is Parshuram about his qualities like kind-heartedness, forgiveness etc. Parshuram's these qualities are hidden because he is under the control of anger. Here Rama is explaining that he is not guilty. One should not be this much angry with the damage to a bow. In this way, he wants forgiveness but is different from Laxmana because he is not using satirical words nor his body language or gesture is insulting.

On the basis of above analysis, the communicative qualities of lord Rama are as follows-

- 1) Establishing Laxmana as a child
- 2) Revealing himself at the right time
- 3) Praising Parshuram
- 4) Showing himself petty
- 5) Keeping body language and gestures accordingly

Bharat Milan

Dasharatha was the father of Rama. He was bound by two promises of her wife, Kaikeyi (stepmother of Rama). She asked for two wishes from Dasharatha; one was to make Bharat king, and the second was to send Rama to the forest for 14 years. When this happened, Bharat was not in Ajodhya. He was at his grandparents. After returning to Ajodhya, he knew what had happened in his absence. He felt very guilty about that because he worshipped his elder brother Rama. Bharat was very upset and angry with his mother, Kaikeyi.

Bharat did not want to become king. He thinks it is Rama's right to be a king. When Rama left the palace and went to the forest and was staying at Chitrakoot, Bharat went there to convince Rama to return to Ajodhya and sit on the throne but failed to convince him. When Bharat reached Chitrakoot, he was blaming himself and his

fate for this tragedy. He was cursing his mother also. Rama dragged Bharat out of his guilt and depression.

In this incident, Rama's statements will be analyzed on how he helped Bharat in going back to Ajodhya and rule after improving his mental situation (Tulsidas).

Firstly, we will see statements of Bharat which will help us understand his mental and emotional condition.

बिधि न सकेऊ सहि मोर दुलारा । नीच बीचु जननी मिस पारा ॥
 यहउ कहत मोहि आजु न सोभा । अपनीं समुझि साधु सुचि को भा ॥
 मातु मंदि मैं साधु सुचाली । उर अस आनत कोटि कुचाली ॥
 फरइ कि कोदव बालि सुसाली । मुकता प्रसव कि संबुक काली ॥
 महीं सकल अनरथ कर मूला । सो सुनि समुझि सहिउं सब सूला ॥
 सुनि बन गवनु कीन्ह रघुनाथा । करि मुनि बेष लखन सिय साथ्था ॥
 बिनु पानहिन्ह पयादेहि पाएँ । संकरु साखि रहेउं एहि चाएँ ॥
 बहुरि निहारि निषाद सनेहू । कुलिस कठिन उर भयउ न बेहू ॥

Meaning

But God could not bear to see the love between us. He used an evil mother to create a difference between us. It is also not suitable for me to say who is a saint or not. My mother is wicked and I am a saint even thinking this is equal to a million evil practices. Can an ear of the Kodo* plant yield good rice and a dark bivalve shell produce a pearl? I suffered all these sorrows because I know I am the cause of all the misfortune. Lord Rama with Laxmana and Sita, went into the woods in hermit's robes on foot without shoes. God Shankara be my witness; I survived even that blow. Witnessing Nishad's love, my hard heart refused to break.

Analysis

Bharat is deeply saddened and shocked by what his mother did. He is blaming God, fate and his mother for Rama's exile. However, suddenly, he started blaming himself. He is blaming himself that he is still alive. He is comparing himself to the rotten fruit of bad plant. These sentences state the fact that Bharat is greatly depressed.

Now we will see Rama's response to Bharat.

बोले गुरु आयस अनुकूला । बचन मंजु मृदु मंगलमूला ॥
 नाथ सपथ पितु चरन दोहाई । भयउ न भुअन भरत सम भाई ॥
 लखि लघु बंधु बुद्धि सकुचाई । करत बदन पर भरत बड़ाई ॥
 भरतु कहहिं सोइ किऐँ भलाई । अस कहि राम रहे अरगाई ॥

तात जायँ जियँ करहु गलानी । ईस अधीन जीव गति जानी ॥
 तीनि काल तिभुअन मत मोरें । पुन्यसिलोक तात तर तोरें ॥
 उर आनत तुम्ह पर कुटिलाई । जाइ लोकु परलोकु नसाई ॥
 दोसु देहिँ जननिहि जड़ तेई । जिन्ह गुर साधु सभा नहिँ सेई ॥
 कहउँ सुभाउ सत्य सिव साखी । भरत भूमि रह राउरि राखी ॥
 तात कुतरक करहु जनि जाएँ । बैर पेम नहिँ दुरइ दुराएँ ॥
 मुनिगन निकट बिहग मृग जाहीं । बाधक बधिक बिलोकि पराहीं ॥
 हित अनहित पसु पच्छिउ जाना । मानुष तनु गुन ग्यान निधाना ॥
 तात तुम्हहिँ मैँ जानउँ नीकें । करौँ काह असमंजस जीकें ॥
 राखेउ रायँ सत्य मोहि त्यागी । तनु परिहरेउ पेम पन लागी ॥
 तासु बचन मेटत मन सोचू । तेहिँ तें अधिक तुम्हार सँकोचू ॥
 ता पर गुर मोहि आयसु दीन्हा । अवसि जो कहहु चहउँ सोइ कीन्हा ॥
 मनु प्रसन्न करि सकुच तजि कहहु करौँ सोइ आजु ।
 सत्यसंध रघुबर बचन सुनि भा सुखी समाजु ॥

Meaning

With the teacher's order, Rama spoke sweet, soft and delightful and harmonized words. the Gurus commands. I swear by you(master) and by the feet of my father that in the whole world, there has been no brother like Bharata. As he is my younger brother, I hesitate to praise him to his face. It will be good for all of us to follow Bharat's advice. Saying so, Rama kept silent. Life is in the hands of God. Brother, you are feeling humiliated unnecessarily. There was no one like you in the past, no one in the present and no one will be in future. He who even thinks about you ruins his life in this world as well as in the next. Those who have not been with gurus or masters only blame their mother, Kaikeyi. Lord Shiva is my witness; I am speaking the truth. Bharat, the earth is being sustained by you. Dear, do not involve in fallacy. Even birds and animals recognize their friends and foe. They go near of hermits but they run as soon as they find the hunter. Humans are more intelligent than animals so I know you are my well-wisher. I know you full well, dear brother; but what am I to do? There is great perplexity in my mind. The king (our father), you know, kept his word and abandoned me; nay, he gave up his life in order to keep his vow of love. I feel perturbed in my mind if I proceed to violate his word; and my scruple on your account is even greater. On top of it, my preceptor has given his command to me. In any case I am prepared to do precisely what you suggest. With

a cheerful heart and shaking off all scruples, tell me what to do; I will accomplish it this very day. The assembly rejoiced to hear these words of lord Rama who was ever faithful to his word.

Analysis

When Bharat came to Rama, he was already tensed. So, it was a perfect step to calm Bharat. Here we can see what Rama said in a very sweet and calming voice. He was behaving very pleasantly with Bharat. Bharat thought that Rama was angry but he was not. Rama is praising Bharat but he is also expressing his awkwardness about praising. Here, he is also giving authority to Bharat by saying that he will follow Bharat's words. Such statements helped in the re-establishment of a sense of belongingness and love of Rama in Bharat's heart. Bharat was very depressed and was blaming himself for the problems which are being faced by Rama, Laxmana and Sita. Here, Rama took all his blame and put it on God. Sometimes it helps in putting the cause of sorrow to a supernatural power or fate. In these situations, people relieve themselves from evil thoughts. Since they are already sad about the situation, it becomes necessary to use these kinds of words. Rama played the role of a good communicator by making these statements.

At the same time, Rama is also praising Bharat by telling his greatness in the world or saying that it is impossible to find a brother like Bharat.

Bharat was blaming his mother, Kaikeyi but Rama denied that it was the mother's fault. He gave a clean chit to Bharat and Kaikeyi by putting this all on fate. In this chaupai, Rama is indicating that Bharat rules the whole world. He also expresses his awareness towards Bharat's love, affection and respect for himself. To emphasize and make his words more authentic, he took an oath of lord Shiva. Also, he is referencing the human mind to support his statement. Again, Rama is expressing his love and confidence towards Bharat. This time he is putting his father's obligation of promises for their exile. He said he is in the forest and could not go home because his father also chose to die for his words. So, following his father, Rama is in a dilemma. Rama is trying to kill Bharat's guilt and put his mind at ease. So, Rama is jumping from God to fate to his father. Repeatedly Rama shares his knowledge of Bharat's love and respects towards

him with Bharat.

Rama's words changed Bharat's mind, which can be seen in his own words.

कीन्ह अनुग्रह अमित अति सब बिधि सीतानाथ ।
 करि प्रनामु बोले भरतु जोरि जलज जुग हाथ ॥
 कहौं कहावौं का अब स्वामी । कृपा अंबुनिधि अंतरजामी ॥
 गुर प्रसन्न साहिब अनुकूला । मिटी मलिन मन कलपित सूला ॥
 अपडर डरेउं न सोच समूलें । रबिहि न दोसु देव दिसि भूलें ॥
 मोर अभागु मातु कुटिलाई । बिधि गति बिषम काल कठिनाई ॥
 पाउ रोपि सब मिलि मोहि घाला । प्रनतपाल पन आपन पाला ॥
 यह नइ रीति न राउरि होई । लोकहुँ बेद बिदित नहिं गोई ॥
 जगु अनभल भल एकु गोसाई । कहिअ होइ भल कासु भलाई ॥
 देउ देवतरु सरिस सुभाऊ । सनमुख बिमुख न काहुहि काऊ ॥
 जाइ निकट पहिचानि तरु छाहुँ समनि सब सोच ।
 मागत अभिमत पाव जग राउ रंकु भल पोच ॥
 लखि सब बिधि गुर स्वामि सनेहू । मिटेउ छोभु नहिं मन संदेहू ॥
 अब करुनाकर कीजिअ सोई । जन हित प्रभु चित छोभु न होई ॥
 जो सेवकु साहिबहि सँकोची । निज हित चहइ तासु मति पोची ॥
 सेवक हित साहिब सेवकाई । करै सकल सुख लोभ बिहाई ॥
 स्वारथु नाथ फिरें सबही का । किऐँ रजाइ कोटि बिधि नीका ॥
 यह स्वारथ परमारथ सारु । सकल सुकृत फल सुगति सिंगारु ॥

Meaning

Lord Rama has done me a great and limitless favour in every way. With joined lotus-like hand and with bowed, Bharata said; What can I say more. You are an ocean of compassion, and you know everything in everyone's heart. Now, as our Guru is happy and you are in my favour, the torment of my foul heart is over. I was obsessed with imaginary fears and my anxiety was foundationless. There is no fault of the sun if someone forgets directions. My ill luck, my mother's crookedness, the odd time and the cruelty of fate, all these had almost ruined me. You came to my rescue by redeeming your vow (of protecting your devotees), a protector of the suppliant you are. This is not a novel procedure for you; it is well-known to the world and is well-established in the Vedas. If the whole world is hostile and you alone on my side, my lord, tell me through whose goodness, if not through yours, can one's good be accomplished? My lord, you are of the same disposition as the tree of paradise: it is

neither for nor against anyone.

Analysis

Bharat's mind and emotions are entirely changed after conversing with Rama. Before talking to him, Bharat was very tense but after Rama's sweet and calming words, he is now relaxed. One of the biggest fears that Rama is angry with him had vanished. He came to take back Rama Ajodhya and was rigid about this but we can see that now he is happy to follow Rama's order. His words explain that he is immensely relieved after talking to Rama.

So, we can say that Rama is an excellent communicator. In this incident, the main motive was to give Bharat emotional stability and mental peace, which was achieved ultimately. After analyzing the statements of lord Rama, the following are the communicative qualities which came forward-

- 6) Calming the tensed and depressed mind of Bharat
- 7) Showing love and affection to Bharat
- 8) Praising Bharat
- 9) Putting out of hand things to fate

Result and discussion

Based on both of the parasangs, the following communicative qualities of lord Rama came to light. The communicative qualities are explained below-

- Establishing Laxmana as a child- Rama repeatedly emphasizes Laxmana being a child. He often compared Laxmana with a child during his conversation with Parshuram. In one of the chaupai, there is a comparison of Laxmana with a wasp. Rama is trying to establish that statements of Laxmana are only mischief and nuisance, and nothing should be taken into notice.
- Revealing himself at the right time- Lord Rama revealed himself to divert Parshuram's anger towards himself. Parshuram was very angry with Laxmana. At first, when Parshuram comes to the court, Rama hides by saying the bow breaker was a servant, but to save Laxmana from Parshuram's rage, Rama accepts that he broke the bow.
- Praising Parshuram- Rama continuously praised Parshuram

by pointing things like Parshuram is Brahman or a man with a kind and big heart. Rama also said that he is feet, Parshuram is head, or his name is small, and Parshuram's name is big. Praising helped Parshuram in calming down.

- Showing himself petty- Rama often compared himself to a servant and Parshuram as owner. Rama was ready to put his axe in Parshuram's axe. He was ready to accept any desire of Parshuram that would help Parshuram leave his anger.
- Keeping body language and gestures accordingly- In the whole conversation with Parshuram, Rama's body language was very polite. He was repeatedly requesting; he was talking with joined hands. Like Laxmana, he was not smiling or using insulting or satirical words. His voice was also very sweet and polite. He also put his head in front of Parshuram's axe.
- Calming the tensed and depressed mind of Bharat- Rama realized that Bharat was in guilt and a tensed situation, so he tried to relax Bharat. From the beginning of conversation, Rama was using words very wisely. He selected words that will help Bharat not the opposite. One thing which threw Bharat in tension is the thought of Rama being angry with him but the statements of Rama filled with love and belongingness which Rama spoke in very polite and relaxed manner calmed Bharat.
- Showing love and affection to Bharat – Rama showed his endless love to Bharat. He said the words like no one could hide love and Bharat's love and respect towards Rama and Rama is well aware of it. So, he must quit cursing his mother or blaming himself for Rama's exile. Rama also gave an example of animals. He explained that animals can identify their friend and enemy and human are more capable of doing such things. These statements established belongingness in Bharat's heart.
- Praising Bharat- Rama can be seen praising Bharat. He is saying it is impossible to find a brother like him. He also called Bharat as the base of world.
- Putting out of hand thing to fate- Bharat was blaming himself and his mother for Rama's exile but Rama put all of these on God. He explained that every incident is under God's control and no one can interfere with God's wish. For a person who

believes in God, such statements are beneficial. Faith in God helps overcome bad times, and words like this are helpful.

- Rama also praise his father who left his life but did not compromise with his promises. This also motivated Bharat which was very much needed.

Conclusion

Rama came out as an excellent communicator who knows how to handle different situations very well. Both the situations were completely different but Rama did very well. He calmed Parshuram, saved Laxmana from his rage, relaxed Bharat, and freed him from guilt. Bharat came to Chitrakoot to take Rama back but he got influenced by Rama and became ready to follow his orders. Rama knew that he is bound with his father's word and if Bharat also lives in exile, then the whole kingdom will be without a king, leading to chaos. Rama was a very good influencer which can be seen in both the prasang. Rama was using examples in both the prasang which were helping in proving his point. Examples are very helpful in explaining thoughts. Comparing Laxmana with wasp shows his sharp mind. Using appropriate gestures is very important in any conversation because a miscommunication can easily happen if wrong gestures are used or if body language is not according. Smiling at bad times is also very harmful. We can say that Rama was a very good communicator who can handle delicate situations and can solve problems only with words and expressions. Communication skills can be learnt from Lord Rama.

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